

Abstract

In this work we used a series of open clusters and associations observed by the **Gaia-ESO Survey (GES)** to study the use of **lithium abundances** (Li I spectral line at 6708 Å) as an age indicator for **pre- and main-sequence FGKM late-type stars**. Previous studies of open clusters have shown that lithium depletion is not only strongly age dependent, but also shows a complex pattern with several other parameters, such as rotation, chromospheric activity and metallicity. Using data from both **GES iDR6** and **Gaia EDR3**, we performed a thorough **membership analysis** and **obtained lists of candidate members for 42 open clusters**, ranging in age from **1-3 Myr to 4.5 Gyr**. We then conducted a comparative study that allowed us to characterise the observable lithium dispersion in each cluster and **study the influence of rotation, activity and metallicity in the lithium dispersion of the selected candidates**. All this allowed us to **calibrate a Li-age relation and obtain a series of empirical lithium envelopes** for 27 of the 42 sample clusters, also constraining the **LDB** for those clusters in the 15-600 Myr age range.

Selection criteria and cluster membership

Candidate members for each cluster are selected from the **Gaia-ESO Survey (GES)** (Gilmore et al. 2012) iDR6 data based on the following criteria: **RVs**, **Gaia** astrometry (proper motions and parallaxes), **gravity indicators** - Kiel ($\log g$ vs T_{eff}) and γ index diagrams -, **[Fe/H]** metallicity, and the position in the **EW(Li) vs T_{eff}** diagram. As an example we show here the case of **IC 2602 (PMs, CMD, EW(Li) vs T_{eff} and γ index)** and **NGC 6705** (RV, Kiel diagram and [Fe/H] histogram):

Cluster candidate selections

EW(Li) vs T_{eff} for the 42 open clusters analysed with data from GES iDR6 (covering a range of age from 1-3 Myr to 4.5 Gyr).

Intermediate-age clusters (50 - 700 Myr)

Dependence with rotation, activity and metallicity. Li-age relation

We used the **rotational velocities ($v \sin i$)**, **chromospheric activity indicators ($EW(\text{H}\alpha)$)** and **[Fe/H]** metallicities provided by GES iDR6, as well as additional rotational periods (P_{rot}) from the literature, including **Kepler, K2 and TESS** measurements. In accordance to prior findings in the literature, **members with higher values of $EW(\text{Li})$ tend to be faster rotators and have higher levels of activity** (for ex., $EW(\text{Li})$ -versus- T_{eff} diagrams above, colour-coded by P_{rot} and $\text{H}\alpha$ for NGC 2516, 125-138 Myr). We additionally did a preliminary assessment on the potential small **effect of metallicity in the Li depletion of coeval clusters** (see top right figure as example), tentatively indicating that metal-rich clusters could show slightly higher Li abundances than their metal-poor counterparts.

Figure 3.26: $EW(\text{Li})$ -versus- T_{eff} diagram comparing the upper Li envelopes for NGC 2244 (4 Myr, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.23$ dex) and NGC 2264 (4 Myr, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.08$ dex).

As we further detail in **Gutiérrez Albarrán et al., 2024b (submitted)**, by taking all these effects into account we calibrated a qualitative **Li-age relation** and created **empirical lithium envelopes** for key age ranges in our cluster sample (see figure, left, showing all 27 final envelopes). As part of this calibration, we also studied the **lithium depletion boundary (LDB)** for clusters in the 15-500 Myr range with the aid of models such as **Baraffe et al. 2015** (see vertical dashed lines in the IC 2602 diagram above). This Li-age calibration will allow us to estimate age ranges for GES field stars.

Old clusters (> 700 Myr)

